

Kornienko Y.*Full Professor, Doctor of Technical Sciences
National Technical University of Ukraine
“Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute”***Tyshko Y.***postgraduate student,
National Technical University of Ukraine
“Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute”
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18070936>***Abstract**

Carotenoid-containing raw materials (carrots, pumpkin, peppers) are valuable sources of natural pigments and bioactive compounds; however, conventional convective drying causes overheating, carotenoid oxidation and quality losses. Recent research highlights the benefits of combined drying technologies (convective, infrared, microwave and vacuum methods with ultrasound assistance), which reduce drying time and specific energy consumption while retaining β -carotene and colour more effectively. Ultrasound decreases external heat- and mass-transfer resistance, shifting the limiting stage to internal moisture diffusion. This provides a basis for optimizing operating parameters and improving the energy efficiency of drying heat-sensitive carotenoid-containing products.

In this regard, the implementation of energy-efficient drying technologies will not only reduce production costs but also lower the carbon footprint of food products – a key factor for accessing markets with strict environmental standards. Moreover, improving the quality and stability of dried raw materials generates higher added value across the supply chain and enhances the global competitiveness of Ukrainian products.

Keywords: carotenoid – containing raw materials, combined drying, ultrasound drying, intensification of drying process, energy efficiency

Carotenoid-containing raw materials (carrots, pumpkin, peppers, etc.) are an affordable source of natural dyes and biologically active substances for, in particular, the food industry [1]. However, traditional convective drying is accompanied by overheating of the material, intense oxidation of carotenoids, loss of color, aroma, and antioxidant activity, which directly reduces the quality and competitiveness of the finished product [1]. Mass transfer during such drying is often limited by a thick boundary layer and high diffusion resistance to moisture movement inside the solid body, which forces an increase in the temperature and duration of the process, increasing specific energy consumption.

A review of domestic and foreign studies shows a steady trend towards the introduction of combined methods of drying carotenoid-containing raw materials (convective, infrared, microwave, vacuum) in combination with ultrasound treatment and other physical influences in order to intensify mass transfer, reducing the duration of the process and energy costs while maintaining the quality of bioactive components [2, 3]. For carrots and pumpkins, it has been shown that the combination of convection with infrared and vacuum drying can significantly reduce drying time and increase the degree of β -carotene preservation with the optimal selection of infrared radiation power and pressure [4, 5, 9]. Studies of combined infrared-vacuum drying of pumpkin confirm that an excessive increase in infrared power leads to the degradation of β -carotene and deterioration of color, therefore, optimization of the modes is necessary [9].

Recent studies on microwave-ultrasound and infrared drying of carrots show a significant reduction in drying time (by 30–60%) and specific energy consump-

tion compared to traditional convection, while maintaining or even increasing the content of carotenoids and color indicators [10, 14]. Some experimental studies on carrot drying using ultrasound confirm higher preservation of β -carotene and vitamin C compared to convective drying [14]. Recent reviews note that ultrasound during the drying of fruits and vegetables reduces the duration of the process by an average of 50%, improves color, texture, bioactive compound content, and recovery capacity, i.e., it is a promising tool for “soft” intensification of heat-sensitive products [12, 14, 17].

However, most of the existing works focus on empirical comparison of individual modes and laboratory prototypes; universal kinetic models of combined drying of carotenoid-containing raw materials, taking into account the degradation of carotenoids and the specifics of ultrasound exposure, have not been sufficiently developed. Many publications either do not take into account the thermal destruction of carotenoids, or the degradation parameters are obtained for conditions that are difficult to scale up to industrial dryers [2, 3, 7]. This limits the possibilities for targeted optimization of the design and operating parameters of drying (temperature, air velocity, ultrasound power and frequency, layer thickness) while taking into account the simultaneous requirement to minimize carotenoid losses and energy consumption.

Compliance with national and international priorities. The National Economic Strategy for the period up to 2030, approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine in March 2021 by Resolution No. 179 (hereinafter referred to as the Strategy), defines the path to innovative, resource-efficient, and export-oriented growth of the Ukrainian economy [9].

The results of the study on the intensification of drying carotene-containing raw materials will directly contribute to the implementation of the Strategy's priority areas, such as the production of products with higher added value, improving energy efficiency and reducing the resource intensity of industrial processes, introducing innovative technologies (in particular, combined drying using ultrasound) in Ukrainian industry, and supporting the export competitiveness of Ukrainian manufacturers.

The relevance of this topic is further enhanced in the context of European climate policy and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). CBAM is an EU instrument that sets a price on carbon emissions "embedded" in certain energy-intensive goods imported into the EU in order to prevent carbon leakage and encourage decarbonization of production in partner countries [15].

Although at this stage CBAM formally applies to a limited group of energy-intensive industries (steel, cement, fertilizers, aluminum, electricity, hydrogen, etc.) [15], analytical reports emphasize that the agricultural and food sectors will be indirectly affected due to the high share of electricity and fertilizers in the carbon footprint of production, and that the list of goods will be expanded in the future [16].

For exporting countries, including Ukraine, one of the recommended strategic directions for adaptation to CBAM is the decarbonization of energy-intensive operations and the improvement of energy efficiency in food technologies [16].

Drying processes in the food industry are among the most energy-intensive mass transfer operations, which significantly shape the carbon footprint of the final product [17].

Also, in a broader context, the results of the work will contribute to the implementation of the goals of the European Green Deal and national decarbonization policy, forming the scientific and technical basis for the modernization of drying equipment and the transition to a "green" food industry.

Intensification of the drying process of carotene-containing raw materials based on combined (convective-ultrasound, microwave, infrared-vacuum) technologies allows not only to improve the quality and biological value of products, but also to reduce specific energy consumption and corresponding CO₂ emissions. This, in turn, contributes to increasing the competitiveness of Ukrainian producers in EU markets during the CBAM and the general strengthening of carbon transparency requirements for supply chains.

Therefore, one of the most promising ways to improve the quality of dried raw materials is to use combined technologies, in particular, the combination of convective heating with ultrasound exposure. Ultrasound intensifies heat and mass transfer on the product surface, shortening the duration of the process and reducing the destruction of thermolabile components (pigments, vitamins).

It should be noted that in order to justify the feasibility of modernizing the drying process from an engineering point of view, it is necessary to assess how ul-

trasound exposure changes the ratio of external and internal transfer resistance, as well as how this affects specific energy consumption. The most informative criterion for determining the limiting phase of heat transfer is the Biot number.

As an example, let us perform some calculations of the Biot number and specific energy consumption for drying carrot slices in traditional and combined modes.

Let us consider drying a carrot slice with a thickness of $\delta = 6$ mm (half-thickness $L = 3$ mm = 0.003 m); sample mass $m_0 = 1$ kg, initial moisture content 88%, dry matter mass $m_{dry} = 0.12$ kg, water mass $m_{water} = 0.88$ kg, initial moisture content $x_0 \approx 7.3$ kg/kg of dry matter, final moisture content $x_k = 0.1$ kg/kg of dry matter, mass of water removed $\Delta m_{water} \approx 0.868$ kg.

Then heat exchange and the Biot number (Bi):

$$Bi = \frac{hL}{k} \quad (1)$$

For raw carrots, a thermal conductivity coefficient of $k \approx 0.34 \dots 0.52$ is taken as a reference and the heat transfer coefficient from the surface of the body to the surrounding environment, for carrots $h_{conv} \approx 20$ W/(m²·K) (typical range 5 – 25 W/(m²·K)):

$$Bi = \frac{20 \cdot 0,003}{0,3} = 0,2 \quad (2)$$

$Bi_{conv} \approx 0.2 > 0.1$, i.e., the resistance inside the product is already significant, but the influence of the outer boundary layer is still significant. The phases of internal thermal conductivity and external convective heat transfer are comparable, but the internal one becomes noticeable.

At the same time, with combined convective-ultrasound drying, the heat transfer coefficient from the surface of the body to the surrounding environment for carrots is $h_{US} \approx 50$ W/(m²·K), then

$$Bi = \frac{50 \cdot 0,003}{0,3} = 0,5 \quad (3)$$

The increase in Bi indicates a transition to a mode where the limiting stage is the internal diffusion of moisture in the capillary-porous structure of carrots, and the external resistance in the boundary layer is significantly reduced.

Given the above, numerical estimates show that when carrot slices are dried with ultrasound, the Bi number increases from ~ 0.2 to ~ 0.5 , i.e., it shifts the limiting stage from external convective heat transfer to internal moisture diffusion, intensifying mass and heat transfer.

Thus, the development of a scientifically based combined method for drying carotene-containing raw materials using ultrasound will contribute to the intensification of mass and heat exchange with minimal risk of carotenoid degradation and a simultaneous reduction in specific energy consumption, confirming the relevance of scientific research. This will create the basis for innovative dryer designs and operating modes that take into account energy efficiency and decarbonization requirements, which is especially important in the context of CBAM implementation and the transition to a green economy.

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